

CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH AMIDES. PART II.
AN ADDENDUM. CONDENSATION OF CINNAMALDEHYDE
WITH *n*-HEPTAMIDE

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In a previous paper (Mehra and Pandya, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 7A, 376, Part II of the series) the condensation of cinnamaldehyde with phenylacetamide, acetamide, benzamide and propionamide have been described, the products being all the *bis*amides. It was also stated that the yields were slightly increased when a trace of pyridine was also taken with them. In the present case the condensation of cinnamaldehyde with *n*-heptamide is described, wherein cinnamylidene-*bis-n*-heptamide is obtained in 42% yield.

Cinnamaldehyde (0.7g.) was heated with 1.4 g. of *n*-heptamide on a water-bath for 9 hours; the contents began to solidify after 5 hours. Next morning, the product was taken out as usual and recrystallised by means of alcohol and water. After several recrystallisations, the product being each time washed with ether, the pure *bis*heptamide came out as colourless crystals melting at 154-55°. It weighed 0.82 g., the yield being thus 42% of theory.

It is insoluble in water, ether, acetone and cold benzene; soluble in hot alcohol and hot benzene. It does not decolourise bromine water in the cold and Baeyer's reagent and gives no colour with concentrated sulphuric acid, thus confirming its *bis*amide nature. (Found N, 7.6. Cinnamylidene-*bis*-heptamide, $C_{23}H_{36}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.4%, the corresponding monoamide requires N, 5.75%.)

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Active Nitrogen—A New Theory : BY S. K. MITRA, D. SC., JOYKISSEN MOOKERJEE MEDAL LECTURER FOR 1945, INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE, CALCUTTA, 1945. ROYAL. 8 *vo* PP. 73. PRICE 5 SH/-.

The book consists of two parts. The first part is a resumé of the characteristic properties and phenomena of active nitrogen studied by different workers ; the second is an enunciation of the author's theory of the nature of active nitrogen molecules, and gives instances where the concept has been useful in explaining observed facts. The author has concluded by making a short reference to what led him to propose his new theory, and by pointing to some yet unexplained facts, e. g., the activity of the "dark modification" and gaps in our knowledge of the subject that have to be filled up.

The book is one of the ablest summaries of the large volume of accumulated experimental material of not infrequently conflicting observations of workers, and especially of the newer and more elaborate methods applied in the second quarter of the century to study the complex phenomenon. The treatment of the problem is illuminating, and the style remarkably lucid.

Since the main purpose of the book, as the name implies, is to acquaint the reader with the author's theory of active nitrogen, other theories have not been as fully treated as one might desire for the purpose of a comparative estimate of their merit. For example, an examination of a suitably modified Sponer's theory is perhaps worthwhile, and might provide a clue to the difficult question of the "dark modification" and to some of the unexplained chemical reactions of the active gas.

The book has been edited and printed with care, with only a few minor errors of print. A notable misprint appears to be $1/\log I$ (p. 15, line 18 *et seq.*), which should be $\log 1/I$, according to the derivation. In the list of references, Strutt's Chemical Society Lecture (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 113, 200) has been an important omission.

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A Text-book of Physical Chemistry : BY DR N. C. SEN GUPTA & MR. K. C. SEN, M. SC. ; MANDAL BROTHERS & Co, LD., CALCUTTA. PRICE RS 10/-.

The authors are to be congratulated for having brought out a compact volume embracing all the important topics in Theoretical Chemistry within a reasonably small compass. The book contains sixteen chapters covering 525 pages. Each chapter contains a bibliography of relevant literature for further study. Although physical chemistry has been mainly dealt with from the classical angle, as most text-books are, reference has often been made to the newer conceptions, which have brought about such radical changes in our ideas. The chapters on Surface Chemistry and Colloids, Liquid State, Constitution of Molecules, etc. deserve particular mention. Brevity of expression which has been necessitated by limited space has, however, in some places been attained at the cost of clarity and it is hoped that the authors will remedy this defect in a subsequent edition.

On the whole, the book will be specially useful to the B. Sc. Honours students of Indian Universities as a preliminary study leading to acquaintance with the more advanced treatises on the subject.

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